

UZBEK PATCHWORK ART AND MEANINGS OF RELATED TERMINOLOGY

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Abstract

The art of patchwork is long-standing manufacturing of various household goods by means of pieces of fabric distributed among the different people of the world. In Europe, this sort of sewing is known under the name of patchwork. This sort of craft was brought to the level of art in the course of time.

Patchwork is also known in Uzbekistan for a long time and it has its own characteristics and traditions. In particular, in divan of Alisher Navoi “Nasoyim ul-mukhabbat” the marakka (patchwork robe, tatter) is often used as dress of holies or dervishes.

Each region of Uzbekistan characterized with its techniques of patchwork. There are many variants and each has its own meaning: “Katlama quroq”, “Turna nuska”, “Kuz”, “Okkush”, “Turna”, “Tegirmon”, “Tirna”, “Kuduk”.

There are a lot of superstitions related to patchworks. For instance, among the local people, on the seventh day of the birth of the child they collect 15 pieces of issue with good intentions from the older’s houses in order “child would live long life as they are, have many children and grandchildren”, they sew small robe from the pieces and wear it to the child till the end of forty days.

By the patchwork technique “Turna”, “Kuz”, “Ulama”, “Katlama”, “Tirna”, “Kuduk”, “Chess” in Surkhandarya. They make accessories for beshik (cradle), curtains, pillowslips, carpets for the feet as a sign of respect. Patchwork products for beshik are made with regards to children’s health, as a talisman against the evil eye. A patchwork carpet for the feet as a sign of special respects, patchwork curtains, one patchwork, 10 patchwork pillows, quroq-bolish (pillow in the shape of the roller) were given to the Bride’s dowry. According to the tradition, the mother in-law makes the mattress from moreover of 100 patches. A small amulet is sewn secretly to another corner. They do it for long life and happiness of newly-weds.

On the occasion of the sunnat toy a couple of pillows, mattress, hurdzun and neck amulets for the horse are sewed from rags.

In some types of patchwork nine patterns are using, indicating in relationship with the Turkic traditions. According to written sources, the number nine considered as sacred in Turkic tribes. Nine identical colorful patterns are embroidered on the product, which is decorated along the circle with different textured patches. A ribbon framing the nine diamond-shaped patterns and edges

of kurpacha, gives integrity and a special rhythm to the product. Pieces of material sewn around the nine squares would fade into the background and not very distinguished.

In every patchwork, not only aesthetics is evident, but also the local features. Scenes of the nature, local coloring and geometric patterns depicted in the patchwork. Ancient patterns, symbols and signs used in the patchwork. Decorative figurative motifs are showing smooth and easy, with the fabrics of warm tones.

Contemporary patch working is a worldwide art and it reflects futures of a culture of all people.

Studying the patchwork helps to reveal sewing schools originality of folk crafts, to learn the traditions and tastes of the sewing masters, and a role of patchwork as the artistic process of applied art.

As science, progressed, new words and terms began to appear in our speech as well. Because of the appearance of Uzbek handicraftsmen on the world stage, words and terms related to Uzbek handicrafts have become widespread. In particular, patchwork and its terms are among them. In this article, we analyze the art of patchwork and its terms.

1) Uz: Quroq [qu-roq] -ulab-qurab, biror narsa hosil qilish uchun yaroqli mato parchasi.

Eng: Patchwork [ˈpætʃwɜ:k] -pieces of cloth of various colors and shapes sewn together to form a covering

2) Uz: Mato [ma-to] -gazlama, material, materiya.

Fabric [ˈfæbrɪk] - a material that resembles cloth

3) Uz: Beshik [be-shik] -Chaqaloqni belab va tebratib uxlatish uchun tol yoki tut yog'ochidan yasalgan yo'rg'a oyoqli maxsus moslama; tebratma belanchak.

Eng: Cradle ['kreɪdl] a bed or cot for a baby usually on rockers or pivots

4) Uz: Yostiqjild [yos-tiq-jild] -yostiqni o'rashda ishlatilgan mato

Eng: Pillowslip ['pɪləʊslɪp] a removable covering for a pillow

5) Uz: Ko'rpacha [ko'r-pa-cha] -O'tirish uchun ostga to'shaladigan, uzun g'ilof ichiga paxta solib qavilgan qalin va yumshoq to'shak.

Eng: Mattress ['mætrɪs] a fabric case filled with resilient material (such as cotton, hair, feathers, foam rubber, or an arrangement of coiled springs) used either alone as a bed or on a bedstead

6) Uz: Qiyqim [qiy-qim] - Gazmolning bichiqdand yoki savdodan ortgan bo'lagi; laxtak.

Eng: Patch [pætʃ] -a piece of material used to mend or cover a hole or a weak spot

7) Uz: Tumor [tu-mor] - Xalqona, diniy tasavvurga ko'ra, go'yo egasini ko'z tegishdan, balo, ofat, ins-jins va shu kabilardan saqlaydigan, ichiga duo bitilgan qog'oz joylangan uchburchak narsa (odatda bo'yinga, qo'lتيqqa, sochga taqiladi yoki kiyimning ichki qismiga tikib qo'yiladi).

Eng: Amulet ['æmjʊlɪt] a charm (such as an ornament) often inscribed with a magic incantation or symbol to aid the wearer or protect against evil (such as disease or witchcraft)

